

CAROTID ARTERY OCCLUSIVE LESIONS AS STROKE PRECURSORS AND THEIR SECONDARY PREVENTION

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Abstract. *Atherosclerotic lesions of the arteries are among the most significant risk factors contributing to the development of stroke. Secondary prevention of stroke aims to avert the progression and recurrence of more severe cerebrovascular events. Alongside therapeutic interventions, surgical correction of carotid artery stenosis namely, carotid endarterectomy (CEA) or carotid angioplasty with stenting (CAS) has demonstrated clinical efficacy in reducing the risk of recurrent strokes.*

Keywords: *stroke, atherosclerosis, stenosis, surgical correction, angiography, carotid endarterectomy, stenting.*

Introduction. The leading cause of ischemic stroke is atherosclerotic stenotic lesions of the extracranial arteries [3]. Secondary prevention of stroke is aimed at preventing the progression of more severe recurrent cerebrovascular disorders. In addition to therapeutic interventions, surgical correction of carotid artery stenosis has proven to be effective [4].

All surgical procedures target the elimination of arterial stenosis and are categorized into two types: carotid endarterectomy (CEA) and, as an alternative, endovascular intervention with stent placement [5,6].

Carotid angioplasty with stenting (CAS) has been used for the prevention of ischemic stroke since the mid-1980s [7], while carotid endarterectomy has been performed since 1954 [8]. Randomized clinical trials such as NASCET, ECST, and ACAS have demonstrated the long-term efficacy of CEA in both symptomatic and asymptomatic patients with significant carotid artery stenosis when compared to conservative medical treatment [9].

Some comparative studies between CAS and CEA have shown advantages in favor of CAS, such as reduced procedural discomfort, shorter hospital stays, and the absence of postoperative scarring compared to CEA [10]. Another significant benefit of the endovascular approach is the lack of need for general anesthesia. Modern fluoroscopic and endovascular techniques in cerebral artery stenting allow for early surgical intervention following disease onset. With careful patient selection, this method has shown high effectiveness, particularly in elderly patients [12]. However, for symptomatic patients, carotid endarterectomy still demonstrates superior clinical outcomes [11].

Thus, despite numerous comparative studies evaluating the results of carotid endarterectomy and carotid artery stenting, the issue of selecting the optimal surgical treatment for patients with carotid artery stenosis remains unresolved.

Further investigation into the risk factors associated with each method is warranted, as well as the development of clear indications for their use in patients with comorbid conditions.

Objective of the Study. To improve treatment outcomes in patients with carotid artery stenosis by selecting the optimal method—carotid endarterectomy (CEA) or carotid artery stenting (CAS)—and to evaluate early and long-term results in patients undergoing these procedures.

Materials and Methods. A total of 238 patients presenting with clinical signs of transient ischemic attack (TIA) were examined. All patients were initially admitted with a diagnosis of TIA. Depending on the chosen treatment strategy, the patients were divided into three groups:

- Group 1: 105 patients received conservative therapy for TIA
- Group 2: 90 patients underwent carotid endarterectomy (CEA)
- Group 3: 43 patients underwent carotid artery stenting (CAS)

The majority of patients were between 41–60 years old (33.4%) and 61–80 years old (55.2%). Across all age groups, male patients predominated. TIA was observed in all major cerebral vascular territories: in the territory of the right middle cerebral artery (MCA) in 41 patients (39.1%), in the left MCA territory in 44 patients (41.9%), and in the vertebrobasilar basin (VBB) in 20 patients (19%). All patients had clear consciousness levels, scoring 15 points on the Glasgow Coma Scale. The mean NIH Stroke Scale (NIHSS) score indicating neurological deficit severity was 7.4 ± 2.0 .

Group 2 (CEA): Ninety patients with TIA underwent carotid endarterectomy. The average age was 61.8 ± 8.8 years. Of these, 72 (80%) were male and 18 (20%) were female. Most patients were aged 41–60 (38.9%) and 61–80 (56.7%). Males predominated across all age groups. The vascular distribution was as follows: TIA occurred in the right MCA territory in 34 patients (37.8%), in the left MCA in 42 (46.7%), and in the VBB in 14 (15.5%). In the conservatively treated group, the average TIA duration was 320.8 ± 249.8 minutes. All patients had a Glasgow Coma Score of 15. The mean NIHSS score was 7.9 ± 2.8 .

Group 3 (CAS): Forty-three patients with TIA underwent carotid artery stenting. The average age was 65.2 ± 7.8 years. Of these, 32 (74.4%) were male and 11 (25.6%) were female. No patients were younger than 40 or older than 81. The majority were aged 41–60 (20.9%) and 61–80 (79.1%). Males predominated in all age ranges. Vascular territories affected included the right MCA in 13 patients (30.3%), the left MCA in 20 (46.5%), and the VBB in 10 (23.2%). In patients receiving conservative treatment, the average duration of TIA was 225.8 ± 192.6 minutes. All patients were alert with a Glasgow Coma Score of 15. The mean NIHSS score was 7.1 ± 2.8 .

All patients underwent standard clinical and neurological assessments:

Neurophysiological and Imaging Assessment Methods:

Neuro-monitoring included dynamic evaluation of neurological status and level of consciousness using standardized scales: the Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS), the National Institutes of Health Stroke Scale (NIHSS), and the modified Rankin Scale (mRS).

Neuroimaging Methods:

Cranial computed tomography (CT) was performed using an “AURALX” scanner (Philips, Netherlands), and multi-slice computed tomography (MSCT) was conducted on the “Brilliance 40” system (Philips, Netherlands).

Conventional Cerebral Angiography:

Cerebral angiography was carried out under aseptic conditions in a dedicated X-ray operating suite equipped with the universal angiographic system Allura Xper FD 20 (Philips). The

procedure was performed via femoral artery access using the Seldinger technique under local anesthesia.

Transcranial Doppler Sonography (TCD):

Cerebral blood flow was evaluated using the MT-1010 system (MINDRAY) with a 2 MHz transducer applied through the temporal “acoustic window.” Parameters assessed included maximum blood flow velocity (Vmax), linear flow velocity (LFV), Gosling’s pulsatility index (PI), and the interhemispheric asymmetry index. The standard examination protocol included large intracranial arteries (anterior, middle, and posterior cerebral arteries) visualized through temporal, occipital, and orbital windows.

Color Duplex Ultrasound Scanning:

Assessment of the major extracranial arteries was performed using the EUB-600 ultrasound system (Hitachi, Japan), equipped with a 7.5 MHz electronic transducer. Parameters measured included peak systolic velocity (PSV, cm/s) and the Pourcelot resistance index (RI).

Statistical Analysis:

All collected data were processed using IBM-compatible computers and analyzed with the "SPSS for Windows" statistical software package. Data were grouped and evaluated using methods of variational statistics.

When determining indications for surgical treatment, several key criteria were considered: the presence of $\geq 70\%$ arterial stenosis, a history of prior ischemic stroke, and the presence of focal neurological symptoms. The degree of arterial lumen narrowing caused by atherosclerotic plaque was assessed using the NASCET (North American Symptomatic Carotid Endarterectomy Trial) methodology based on angiographic imaging.

In a subset of patients diagnosed with carotid artery stenosis exceeding 70%, transluminal balloon angioplasty (TLBA) and stenting of the internal carotid artery were performed with the use of distal embolic protection devices. Restoration of the arterial lumen with a residual stenosis of less than 30% was regarded as a technical success of the endovascular intervention (Figures 1 and 2).

Figure 1 – Before the surgery

Figure 2 – After the surgery

All patients were prescribed dual antiplatelet therapy consisting of 75 mg of clopidogrel per day and 100-150 mg of acetylsalicylic acid 3-5 days before the procedure. In the case of urgent interventions, a loading dose of 600 mg of clopidogrel was given once. During the procedure, heparin was administered at a dose of 5000-10000 IU, depending on the patient’s weight and the duration of the intervention.

Angiographic examination, TLBAP, and carotid artery stenting were performed in a fluoroscopy suite on the Allura Xper FD 20 Philips angiographic scanner, using the automatic

injector Mark V Provis Plus Medrad. Most procedures were performed under local infiltration anesthesia; however, in two cases, general endotracheal anesthesia was required due to the severity of the patients' condition and motor agitation. Access to the vascular system was achieved by puncturing the common femoral artery. A 6-8 Fr guide catheter or introducer was placed in the distal segment of the internal carotid artery. Digital subtraction angiography was performed in most cases in standard projections – anteroposterior and lateral – at a speed of 3 frames per second, capturing arterial, parenchymal, and venous phases of the study. In unclear cases, rotational angiography with three-dimensional reconstruction was also performed for more detailed qualitative and quantitative vessel analysis.

After selecting the working projection and under Roadmapping function control, a distal embolic protection device, such as SpiderFX Medtronic, Emboshield NAV6 Abbott, or FilterWire Boston Scientific, was positioned in the petrous portion of the internal carotid artery. Subsequently, self-expanding carotid stents, such as Precise Cordis, Acculink and XACT Abbott, Wallstent Boston Scientific of various diameters and lengths, were implanted in the area of the atherosclerotic plaque, ensuring the coverage of an unchanged segment. If residual stenosis of more than 30% remained, post-dilatation was performed using a monorail balloon catheter with a diameter of 4.5-6.5 mm (Viatrac 14 Abbott, Aviator Plus Cordis, and Mozec Meril). After removal of the distal embolic protection system, a control angiography was conducted to assess the procedure and monitor possible complications.

Manual hemostasis at the puncture site was carried out in the intensive care unit, where the patient was transferred for hemodynamic monitoring for 4-6 hours. The following day, patients were mobilized after the removal of the pressure bandage.

Carotid endarterectomy (CEA) was performed under endotracheal anesthesia. In all cases, neuroprotective medications were used to protect the brain from ischemia, including antihypoxants and membrane stabilizers (dexamethasone, thiopental sodium, ceraxon, actovegin). Moderate arterial hypertension was induced (by 20-25 mmHg above baseline values), while in hypertensive patients, baseline levels were maintained. When studying blood flow velocity in the middle cerebral artery (MCA) under normotension and artificially induced hypertension, it was found that an increase in blood pressure by 20-25 mmHg from baseline was associated with a parallel increase in blood flow through the MCA. In cases of bilateral lesions, surgery was performed on the affected side.

Results and Discussion. No significant complications (stroke, myocardial infarction) or deaths were noted during the early postoperative period (within one month) following carotid artery stenting, except for one episode of transient ischemic attack (TIA), which occurred after angioplasty in the area of the implanted stent. This patient had several complicating factors: occlusion of the contralateral internal carotid artery, hemodynamically significant stenosis of both vertebral arteries, poorly controlled hypertension, and three episodes of TIA within two weeks prior to admission. Neurological symptoms, including right-sided hemiparesis and dysarthria, which developed in the fluoroscopy suite, resolved within 4 hours and were likely caused by decompensation of cerebral blood flow during balloon catheter inflation in the artery supplying both hemispheres. A brain CT scan immediately after the procedure and 24 hours later showed no fresh ischemic changes. Transient hypotension and bradycardia during the procedure were observed in 9 patients and were managed by administering atropine sulfate and sympathomimetics. Vascular spasm of the internal carotid artery, caused by the placement/removal of the embolic

protection system basket, was seen in 7 patients during control angiography but did not necessitate any further intervention. In two cases, moderate contrast-induced encephalopathy developed, which was treated with medication. Three patients developed large (greater than 10 cm) subcutaneous hematomas at the puncture site, which did not require surgical intervention.

Neurologically, positive dynamics were observed, with a regression of focal neurological symptoms in patients with ischemic-type acute cerebrovascular accidents (CVA), who underwent surgery during the acute period (the "therapeutic window"). In the remaining patients, focal symptoms persisted but their general condition stabilized.

After carotid endarterectomy (CEA), intraoperative ischemic disturbances in the brain were noted in two cases post-surgery. In the first case, an ischemic stroke occurred, leading to a fatal outcome. In the second case, a transient ischemic attack (TIA) was observed due to a persistent critical stenosis of the contralateral carotid artery. In the remaining patients, a good outcome was noted, with stabilization of their general condition and regression of neurological symptoms. Specifically, in patients with an initial Rankin scale score of 3-4, their condition improved to a score of 0-1 after surgical treatment.

Postoperative bleeding from the wound in the early postoperative period was observed in two patients, requiring repeat intervention. Wound revision and hemostasis were performed, and in both cases, the wounds healed by primary intention.

Conclusions and Summary.

1. The choice of treatment strategy was based on the following criteria: age, clinical manifestations, collateral circulation capabilities, the condition of the atherosclerotic plaque as assessed by duplex scanning, and the nature and severity of comorbidities.

2. Angioplasty and carotid artery stenting (CAS) should be performed according to the same indications as traditional carotid endarterectomy (CEA).

3. Stenting is indicated for isolated stenoses of both or one carotid artery greater than 60% in symptomatic disease, which in the past was associated with frequent transient ischemic attacks (TIAs), and greater than 70% in asymptomatic patients.

4. Angioplasty with subsequent stenting should be preferred when there are serious contraindications to performing CEA due to comorbid conditions.

5. Absolute contraindications to CAS include individual intolerance to contrast agents; in symptomatic patients, CEA remains the preferred method.

6. Transluminal balloon angioplasty and carotid artery stenting with distal embolic protection is a minimally invasive and non-traumatic method for treating atherosclerotic carotid artery disease and may serve as an alternative to carotid endarterectomy.

7. Successfully performed CEA and CAS equally and reliably reduce the risk of potential stroke development.

8. The best clinically significant results are achieved when surgical treatment is performed during the stages of reversible ischemic neurological deficits (TIA, "minor stroke"), rather than in patients with completed strokes.

9. Regression of neurological symptoms, restoration of blood flow, and the absence of further acute cerebral circulation disturbances or transient attacks promote the continued use of these methods in patients with cerebrovascular disorders. Further studies of the long-term results of these methods are necessary.

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